

MODERN METHODS OF STUDYING ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Abstract. *Learning English is very important today. In most countries of the world, English is widely used in diplomacy, business and commercial documentation. It is one of the five official languages of the UN along with French, Spanish, Russian and Chinese, and one in seven people in the world knows or is learning English. The study of a foreign language is mandatory in every higher education institution and is based on two main aspects - teaching vocabulary and grammar.*

Key words: *Grammar, number, question-answer, continuity, constancy.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ГРАММАТИКИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Изучение английского языка очень важно сегодня. В большинстве стран мира английский язык широко используется в дипломатии, деловой и коммерческой документации. Это один из пяти официальных языков ООН наряду с французским, испанским, русским и китайским, и каждый седьмой человек в мире знает или изучает английский язык. Изучение иностранного языка является обязательным в каждом высшем учебном заведении и базируется на двух основных аспектах – обучении лексике и грамматике.*

Ключевые слова: *Грамматика, число, вопрос-ответ, непрерывность, постоянство.*

INTRODUCTION

English Grammar For a beginner, this may seem overwhelming. Articles, pronouns, verbs - there are many rules in English that are not easy to translate into Russian. This raises doubts, but is it worth starting at all? Is it worth it to go deeper if you are not sure that you can master English grammar? No, you won't get far with this attitude. Therefore, it is important to abandon all doubts and stereotypes. Trust me, you can learn English grammar by yourself and in no time. All that is required of you is perseverance and determination, and we will help you with everything else.

At first glance, English grammar may seem like the most difficult set of rules to learn. But, believe me, the real truth is not like that! As complex, confusing and boring as English grammar may seem, it can be one of the simplest and easiest things in the world that you learn in seconds. For this, only your desire is enough!

In simple words, everything in English is its grammar. Accordingly, the frequently asked question, how to learn grammar, has a very simple answer: to learn English grammar, you only need to learn the language. Of course, it will not be possible to analyze all the nuances in one article. After all, even those books that promise to show you the whole grammar of the English language from scratch with exercises, in fact, will never tell you the whole grammar. Therefore, we have collected only the most basic rules, most suitable for beginners.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Grammar is a tool that can be used to describe any language. Grammar gives names to words (words) and phrases (phrases) that make up sentences (sentences). In early childhood, we learn to build sentences - the grammar of our native language is subordinate to everyone. When

studying English at school, university, with a tutor or at home, we are once again faced with the need to walk this path on our own and consciously. And here we need to have an idea about the types of words and phrases and how they are added to sentences.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To learn English grammar thoroughly and most importantly easily in a few months, follow these proven, reliable and simple instructions that give absolutely good results:

1. Before learning English grammar, learn Uzbek grammar well. A person who does not know his native language cannot perfectly learn a foreign language. It's great that you started learning English grammar, but it will be easier for you to learn the grammar of a foreign language if you first learn Uzbek grammar or review your existing knowledge. Even though Uzbek and English grammars differ greatly in structure, origin and study, the basic grammatical concepts used in language learning are the same in these two languages. Therefore, one can better understand English grammar by comparing, contrasting and combining common concepts. The better you know your native language, the better you understand the rules of its grammar, the easier it is to learn English grammar.

2. Don't learn English. Live English! It is very difficult to understand the grammar of a language just by studying it. To learn English grammar easily, it is not enough to memorize grammar rules, read grammar books, or attend boring grammar lessons over and over again. The first step to making learning grammar easier is to understand the meaning of each rule of the language by feeling the structure of the grammar with your whole body. In a word, in order to learn grammar, you need to understand it enough to feel it with your whole body, and you need to be able to introduce this concept into your mental life. How can this be done? Imagine that you want to study the topic of numbers in English grammar. To do this, you should not be limited to reading only the rules about numbers. Take a pen and a new sheet of paper and create for yourself the simplest, most understandable, most interesting rule you can imagine on this topic. Write additional terms as needed. Well, what you write should not be as complicated as in books, the main thing is that it should be natural and in harmony with your views! You will see that concepts of a numerical topic will begin to appear that are suitable for you, understandable and, most importantly, convenient for you to study. Thus, you can easily start learning English grammar according to your wishes, style and views, adapting each topic to suit you. It's not about the external environment. The most important thing is your attitude towards the work you are doing!

3. Study your learning. What teaching method do you learn best? Understand this very well. Some people learn best by listening, others by seeing or doing. If you find it easy to learn by ear, you can record the audio of your reading grammar rules on your phone's voice recorder and then listen to it all day long. If you are good at learning by watching, learn English grammar with slides and video lessons. If you find it easier to learn by doing, try doing the exercises on the topic more than usual and practice the learned grammar rule more often.

4. Effectively use the knowledge you have. Your Russian is good? If you know, you can effectively use this knowledge in the process of learning English! You know perfectly well how close Russian grammar is to English. You can use this ratio to gain new knowledge by comparing two languages. How many new concepts can be learned in the process of carefully studying the similarities and differences between English and Russian grammar!

5. Study with a friend. It is much more efficient to learn by competing or sharing ideas than by learning alone. Keep in touch with your English grammar friend as often as possible. Frequently ask him questions and answers on grammatical topics. If you do not have a close acquaintance or friend to study English grammar, such a partner can be your peers studying at local language centers, students of the university where you study, and in the most difficult cases, users of English language learning sites. on the Internet, for example, you can find a partner for joint language learning among members of English language learning groups on the Odnoklassniki website. The wish always finds a way!

CONCLUSION

6. Don't be afraid to make mistakes Did you know that learning grammar is about constantly making mistakes and understanding them by correcting them? If you don't know, you will feel bad when you make mistakes while doing exercises on a particular topic while studying grammar, you will lose motivation to learn, and as a result, you will not spend more energy on studying. you can spend it regretting your mistakes. And when you know that learning from mistakes is fun, rewarding, and memorable, those negative feelings will never stop you! Never be afraid to make mistakes when learning English grammar. Try to express your opinion on the topic, even if there is a possibility of being wrong.

7. Review what you've learned often It's better to spend 3 minutes every day reviewing a grammar rule you've learned once than to spend 3 hours once a week. Focus on how often you repeat, not how long you repeat! Don't forget that if you don't review what you've learned, you can quickly get out of this knowledge! Only repetition will strengthen your knowledge. You can test your knowledge by completing the grammar exercises in English grammar exercises, by reading the grammar rules, or by taking grammar tests with a friend.

8. Learn by teaching You may not have mastered English grammar yet, but you may have memorized the smallest and simplest concepts. In this case, it is very important for your own learning to explain grammar rules that you know well to your younger brother, acquaintance or complete stranger who is interested in learning English. To teach someone something, you need to repeat this knowledge over and over again, explore and look for simpler ways to better explain. This means that you will automatically repeat the topic and firmly grasp it. You don't need to be a great teacher, you don't need to be proficient in English to teach English to someone. Start passing on your knowledge to someone else today! The above tips for learning English are just some of the thousands of ways to learn English. Other than that, there are many ways to learn English easily. Finding them requires research, patience and effort.

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